

Quest for identify & cultural acknowledgement in novels of Jumphalahari's Name sake and We are Displaced by Malala Yousafzai

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Abstract

This paper attempts to study how in **Jumphalahari's Name sake** and **We are Displaced by Malala Yousafzai** reconnoiters identity quest by means of cultural acknowledgement. Jhumpa Lahiri is an Indo-American writer who writes and talks about the experiences of the first generation and second generation migrants. Her novel *The Namesake* profoundly depicts the struggle of its various characters which is inner (psychological) and outer as well as the overall transnational, trans-cultural experiences of migrant Indo- Americans. In **'The Namesake'** the whole story revolves around one central issue and that is name and a quest for the true identity. In this regard, Stuart Hall's notion of identity as the continuous play of history, culture and power- and Homi K. Bhabha's concept of "third dimension" as the common ground for negotiation and transformation, which is neither assimilation nor otherness but represents the history of coalition building and the transnational and cultural diasporic connection are very important sources to understand and analyze this novel. The novel focuses on the notion of transitional identities.

We Are Displaced: True Stories of Refugee Lives in this uplifting work Yousafzai shares the survival stories of female refugees from around the world. Before she was a Nobel Peace Prize winner, Yousafzai was displaced. When she was just 11-years-old, the Taliban forced Yousafzai and her family to leave their idyllic home in the Swat Valley and join the ranks of Pakistan's Internally Displaced Persons. Yousafzai recounts the agony of leaving behind her books, friends, and pet chickens and the disappointment of interrupted schooling. She also vividly describes the horror of seeing schools reduced to rubble as a result of bombings, an experience that both politicized her and forced her family into exile in England. The author devotes only about a quarter of the book to her own story, the remainder is a collection of oral histories from displaced women and girls from countries ranging from Yemen to Colombia to the Democratic Republic of Congo. Each refugee's tale of survival is equal parts devastating and inspiring, and the narrators do not shy away from the complex, contradictory experiences of fleeing a homeland. The narratives are filled with emotionally specific descriptive details that render each voice powerful and unique. In the prologue, Yousafzai

specifically states that her purpose is to transform refugees from nameless, faceless statistics into who they really are: humans whose identities are more than just their displaced status

Key words: Transitional Identity, Transnational, Jumpalahari, Name sake, We are Displaced, Malala Yousafzai.

Introduction

Malala is shot in the head by the Taliban on October 9, 2012 on her way to school. Zaynab flees Yemen with her sister Sabreen, for fear of a stray bullet in the streets. Sabreen watches as Zaynab boards a plane to America without her, because for reasons unknown Sabreen's visa wasn't approved. Muzoon, her city under siege for two years, runs from Syria. Najla escapes captivity in ISIS, just as she did her father when he tried to forbid her schooling. Maria, a true *luchadora*, flees with her mother and siblings from Columbia. Analisa travels on her own, away from oppression in Guatemala, all whilst thanking God for her blessings. Marie Claire seeks refuge twice, first from the Congo and then Zambia, before working tirelessly in America to graduate high school to honor her slain mother.

In Malala Yousafzai's new book, *We Are Displaced*, Malala recounts her own notorious tale of displacement before handing the pen to eight other resilient young female refugees. *We Are Displaced* provides these women the opportunity to tell their stories like no media coverage ever could, to effectively communicate what it truly means to be dis-placed.

Jhumpa Lahiri represents her characters struggling hard to balance the two worlds along with the issues of immigration, race, culture and identity. The novel gives a deep insight into the life journey of a migrant Bengali couple in America. In this novel every character seems little lost and contemplating all the time. Main protagonist, Ashima always keeps brooding on the rift between Indian and American culture and always felt the tinge of unhomed space. She always keeps comparing all the situations and wished to be in the closure of her family in India. Specially, whenever she gets emotional, she realises what it is to be in foreign, away from own social and cultural roots. Her conscience gets pricked and feels alienated, uprooted and often nostalgic. Ashima who always experiences the tinge of complex psychological problems like sense of rootlessness, alienation in foreign land where she got migrated at the tender age and feels related to no one. She always longed for the closure of her family specially in such situation when she is expecting a child. Ashima finds it very difficult to live in a place which doesn't belong to her. She has lot of apprehensions about her subsequent life conditions in America. She felt totally miserable when she even thought of giving birth to a child in such alien land. It is evidently clear from the following remark. Throughout her pregnancy, Ashima was afraid of raising a child in "a country where she is related to no one, where she knows so little, where life seems so tentative and spare." (6) It clearly shows her predicament and carves for familial environment. So, in such unfamiliar scenario it becomes quite difficult for her to be at perfect peace. Initially she is very sensitive, sentimental and typical submissive Indian woman who always prefers to follow the Indian tradition and culture. Her life moves around her family only. She always wished that her son should also follow the Indian culture and must have all the sensibilities and respect towards their own Indian culture and its social ethos. However, she feels disheartened when she doesn't find desirable response from her son. Later in the novel she emerges as a strong character that embarks on her journey without worrying much about future course. Her personality takes a significant change after the death of her husband and there is a visible transition in her overall personality and perceptions. Now, she takes the charge of her

life boldly to counter all upheavals of the life even in alien surrounding. By the end of this novel she decides spending half time in both the locations, America and India. In all, she feels the pull of different cultures, tradition and social scenario. At first she is not much confident, always in dilemma and confusion but eventually after living for a long time in different spaces she brings the confidence home and starts taking decisions. At the end of the novel Ashima's change has been projected in the following way: *She has learned to do things on her own, and though she still wears saris, still puts her long hair in a bun, she is not the same Ashima who had once lived in Calcutta. She will return to India with an American passport. In her wallet will remain her Massachusetts driver's license, her social security card.* (276). It shows the transformation of Ashima towards her independence which is the result of her encounters in unhomed space.

Objective:

This paper intends to explore and analyze novels of **Jumpalahari's** Name sake and **We are Displaced** by **Malala Yousafzai** acknowledging cultural diversity provisions the struggle for **identity** and communication is manifested

We Are Displaced ; Continuing activism

In this powerful and emotional *New York Times* bestseller, Nobel Peace Prize winner and activist Malala Yousafzai shares various stories of displacement, including her own. Part memoir, part communal storytelling, *We Are Displaced* introduces readers to some of the incredible girls Malala has met on her many journeys and lets each tell her story - girls who have lost their community, relatives and often the only world they've ever known, but have not lost hope.

Longing for home and fear of an uncertain future binds all of these young women, but each is unique. In a time of immigration crises, war and border conflicts, *We Are Displaced* is an important reminder that every single one of the 79.5 million currently displaced is a person - often a young person - with dreams for a better, safer world. As in, out of *place*—out of the ground they used to walk every day, the air they used to breathe. “I feel the calm earth beneath my feet,” Malala writes, reminiscing about the childhood home she knew before the Taliban invaded Swat Valley. The ground itself is extremely communicative in this book: it is capable of instilling a sense of peace, a family's love, home—or fear, as it quakes and rumbles with violence. Foreign ground is tricky too. Foreign ground can be shockingly cold, for feet that have only ever touched Middle Eastern soil, or empty, for feet accustomed to loved-one's company.

The ground can be home, but even home can be the enemy. Terrorism and organized violence are not the only evils from which the narrators of *We Are Displaced* flee, and it is no coincidence that all the book's narrators are women. In some of their communities, the girls are “displaced” just by nature of being female, discriminated against by the people who love them most dearly.

Individual's identity and assimilation of culture

It is mainly through Gogol; Lahiri presents the identity crisis or conflicts which she herself has faced deeply. It is Lahiri's lifelong mixed feelings about her identity due to her Indian name which gives base to Gogol's struggle in the novel. As the title '*The Namesake*' itself suggest that it primarily discusses the issue of forming one's own identity in the changing social and cultural scenario and to explore the power that a name can carry which ultimately decides an individual's identity and assimilation into a particular social and cultural set up. *Terry Eagleton writes in, The Idea of Culture (2000) that the very word culture contains a tension between making and being made. They keep struggling for cultural identity which sways between two countries. Parents talk of shared history which stresses oneness. But cultural identity lies not only in oneness but in "critical points of deep and significant difference which constitute what we really are; or rather – since history has intervened – what we have become."* (Hall 112) Gogol and many other characters in 'The Namesake' face a continual dilemma as faced by the all immigrants while coming to new land. They struggle to maintain their identities while coming into the contact with new cultural values at the same time. This is what, whole second generation in America must have experienced. They feel sandwiched between the country of their parents and the country of their birth. They struggle to strike a balance between the ideologies and social ethos of these two countries. They find themselves quite a stranger at both the locations. In India they are considered Americans and in America they are taken as Indians. Due to this dilemma they encounter identity crisis and struggle to counter this tantalizing situation. This conflict is clear in following observation. *"The first generation's story was about adaptation and learning acculturing and also discovering new things about themselves. The second generation finds itself presented with two conflicting realities and cultures and sets of expectations – one of the host countries through the socio-cultural surroundings and the other of the home country through their parents."* (Batra 50)

This dilemma in Lahiri's mind is well reflected through the character of Gogol. She focuses on the generational differences, conflicts and the flowing nature of identities amidst the feeling of up rootedness and indifferent attitude of host culture. Gogol's inner struggle for his true identity intensifies with the issue of his name, which he finds very unusual. Especially in his teenage Gogol finds it very embarrassing to have such name which sounds much awkward to him and doesn't give him a feel of ease and any sign of cultural linkage to particular social identity. So, Gogol decides to change his name to Nikhil before going to college which further shows his ardent desire to take the control of his own identity. He finds his existing name 'Gogol' very repulsive and starts hating this name. It is a direct outcome of the identity confusion at his birth, when the letter carrying his 'True Name' got lost in the mail. His father Ashok gives him name after his favourite Russian author which holds a deep significance for him but, Gogol is not clearly told about this emotional link very clearly during his childhood. However, in his formative days he was fine tuned with his name Gogol and rather insisted at school that he wishes to carry the same name, as being Nikhil he found himself an another person. He takes it as if someone is robbing his real identity from him. He is actually afraid of his new name. When his parents wished his name Nikhil to be his official name, he declines to accept the new name. It was his first attempt to reject a dual identity.

Doubts and apprehensions in cultural acknowledgement

As a child he associates a new name with a new identity and new reflection on him and he feels literally confused with the existing situation. However, this rejection left him alone with his old name Gogol. But, gradually, he realizes the uncommon nature of his name which problematizes his perception of identity when he grows up. He dislikes to be known by a name which sounds neither Indian, nor American. He always wishes to be identified as common American but he does not feel like an American with this strange sounding name. After knowing about his namesake, the Russian Author, he becomes too desperate to get rid of his name. His name Gogol “sounds ludicrous to his ears, lacking dignity of gravity.” (76) He does not feel like reading Nikolai Gogol as he thinks it “would mean paying tribute to his namesake, accepting it somehow” (92). Actually, He doesn’t bother about his unique name till he reaches to eleven and later during a class trip to a cemetery he first realizes that his name sounds very different and dissociative to existing cultural pattern. He doesn’t find it related to the main stream American as well as the Indian culture. Consequently, he starts hating his name to greater extent by taking it as a threat for his identity and becomes aware of the oddity of his name. He starts realising that being Gogol, he stands nowhere. It starts creating lots of doubts and apprehensions in his tender mind. His sensibilities start questioning and he feels an abnormal unease with this name. He becomes so obsessed with this inner conflict that he goes and changes his name legally which ultimately gives him a sigh of relief. Later when he enters Yale, nobody knows his earlier identity as Gogol. Now he feels relaxed and confident and his transformation starts. He starts doing many things which otherwise he couldn’t dare to do as Gogol. But, a new problem confronts him. He changes his name still “he does not feel like Nikhil” (105). He fears to be discovered being Gogol. So, he hates everything that reminds him of his affairs in past. But the loss of the old name was not so easy to forget and when he visits his home “Nikhil evaporates and Gogol reenters again.” (106) The transition in Gogol’s identity is also the result of divides between his family’s Indian cultural ethos and his progressing desire to be modern, independent and to follow American life style. In the novel there is a constant striving for a clear identity and his struggle becomes more intense due to his venture into the culturally divided world in which he grows up. He feels pull from the both sides. Gogol’s many of the decisions seem governed by the desire to live a normal American life and to escape the continual pull of his family’s tradition. Specially, in his relation with Maxine, an upper class modern girl, he finds solace and alternative home. He prefers to vacations with her family instead of visiting his family which he ignores. Gogol is completely torn between the choice of respecting their Indian culture and the mainstream American culture wherein he grows up.

Father has given him a name ‘Gogol’ due to its close connection with his chance survival in the fatal train accident earlier in his life. But, Gogol wasn’t mature enough to understand its deep emotional link at that time. His father tries a lot to convince him about the significance of his name and its true associative value, but Gogol keeps a reluctant attitude towards such revelation. “*For his father had a point; the only person who didn’t take Gogol seriously, the only person who tormented him, the only person chronically aware of and afflicted by the embarrassment of his name, the only person who constantly questioned it and wished it were otherwise, was Gogol*” (100). In his later life at college he uses his new name ‘Nikhil’ only which he feels has given him a new transformed identity, confidence and freedom. Still, sometimes he feels that untold ache of dual personality whenever he feels that actually he is Gogol in the guise of Nikhil. It shows that it’s not easy to get rid of our past and it keeps bouncing back. In this ways he keeps swinging between past and present.

The Namesake, We Are Displaced: A Struggle for Identity

"What's in a name?" goes the old, beautiful Shakespearean quote: "That which we call a rose / By any other name would smell as sweet." However, when it comes to questions of identity, it turns out names are more loaded than Juliet assumed. In the context of [Jhumpa Lahiri](#)'s novel *The Namesake* (2003), a name is not just a label on a person: it is a whole self. Thus, names and namesakes are paramount in the novel, and substituting one for the other is also like throwing off an old self and forging a new one. Therefore, its title: *The Namesake*.

As the book opens, Ashima and Ashoke Ganguli, young Bengali immigrants to Boston, have had a son. The year is 1968. Names for newborn babies are typically chosen by Bengali elders, but in the case of Ashima and Ashoke, the word on this matter from their own parents is still a month away. So Ashima and Ashoke decide to tide the wait over with choosing a pet name, which in Bengali is known as a daknam.

Malala Yousafzai became an international symbol of the fight for girls' education after she was shot in 2012 for opposing Taliban restrictions on female education in her home country of Pakistan. In 2009, Malala had begun writing a blog under a pseudonym about the increasing military activity in her home town and about fears that her school would be attacked. After her identity was revealed, Malala and her father Ziauddin continued to speak out for the right to education.

The Taliban's attack on Malala on 9 October 2012 as she was returning home from school with her friends received worldwide condemnation. In Pakistan, over 2 million people signed a right to education petition, and the National Assembly ratified Pakistan's first Right to Free and Compulsory Education Bill.

In 2013, Malala and her father co-founded the Malala Fund to bring awareness to the social and economic impact of girls' education and to empower girls to demand change. In December 2014, she became the youngest-ever Nobel Peace Prize laureate. Secretary-General António Guterres designated Malala as a United Nations Messenger of Peace in 2017 to help raise awareness of the importance of girl's education. And her identity as the girl blogger from Swat eventually became known as she became more vocal on the subject of the right of girls to education. It is a subject she never ceased to be passionate about even after she returned home once the militants had been run out of Swat. In 2009 a documentary film was made about her. Many more honours followed: in 2011 she was nominated for the International Children's Peace Prize by The KidsRights Foundation and in 2012 the Pakistani government awarded her the National Peace Award - subsequently renamed the National Malala Peace Prize - for those under 18 years old. After the BBC diary ended, Yousafzai and her father were approached by New York Times reporter Adam B. Ellick about filming a documentary. In May, the Pakistani Army moved into the region to regain control during the Second Battle of Swat. Mingora was evacuated and Yousafzai's family was displaced and separated. Her father went to Peshawar to protest and lobby for support, while she was sent into the countryside to live with relatives. "I'm really bored because I have no books to read," Yousafzai is filmed saying in the documentary.

That month, after criticising militants at a press conference, Yousafzai's father received a death threat over the radio by a Pakistani Taliban commander. Yousafzai was deeply inspired in her activism by her father. That summer, for the first time, she committed to becoming a politician and not a doctor, as she had once aspired to be.

By early July, refugee camps were filled to capacity. The prime minister made a long-awaited announcement saying that it was safe to return to the Swat Valley. The Pakistani military had pushed the Pakistani Taliban out of the cities and into the countryside. Yousafzai's family reunited, and on 24 July 2009, they headed home. They made one stop first – to meet with a group of other grassroots activists that had been invited to see United States President Barack Obama's special representative to Afghanistan and Pakistan, Richard Holbrooke. Yousafzai pleaded with Holbrooke to intervene in the situation, saying, "Respected ambassador, if you can help us in our education, so please help us." When her family finally did return home, they found it had not been damaged, and her school had sustained only light damage

Conclusion

Identity is an inseparable part of our social recognition and status. It allows us to venture into the realm of social fabrics. Every individual always prefers to have a strong and well defined social standing in particular section of any society. Still there are factors which come into play and make the identity of any individual a continual process of shaping and redefining in any changing social scenarios. Readers of *We Are Displaced* will learn of girls who burn themselves alive for fear of their fathers' punishment, girls who run away from home because their fathers have forbid them from going to school, and girls who learn from each other—rather than their parents or communities—that marriage is not their only future. “You and me, we can be the ripple effect. If we go to school, others will follow,” a young girl tells Muzoon, clasping the other girl's hands in solidarity. Each narrator works persistently to create her own agency and her own sense of home, despite the violence and oppression beating down upon her.

Malala cheers every one of them forward in the form of a thoughtful preface to each chapter. She reminds Muzoon, “If you lose your hope, you will be able to look at yourself and what you've already accomplished. You are already powerful.” These words, written in simple but heartfelt and poignant prose, serve as a reminder to the book's young readers as well. *You are already powerful*. To promote the power of all women everywhere, proceeds from the book will be used to support the Malala Fund's work for girls' education. *We Are Displaced*, timely and heart-wrenching, asks only for empathy for the thousands of girls fleeing across dangerous terrain towards freedom and school as you read these words.

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